

PORTRAYAL OF WOMEN IN GITHA HARIHARAN'S THE THOUSAND FACES OF NIGHT

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to delve into the inner lives of Indian women in Githa Hariharan's *The Thousand Faces of Night*. It examines the current state of women's rights. A close examination of this novel reveals that the novelist depicts the dismal predicament of middle and lower middle class women under India's patriarchal societal setup. These women are either from the city or from the countryside. They are either modern or archaic in their attitudes. The narrative centres on three female characters, Devi, Mayamma, and Sita, who are persecuted as a result of patriarchal oppression. Githa Hariharan has purposefully interwoven the stories of mythical women such as Gandhari, Kunti, Sita, Amba, and others to highlight the nature and degree of myths' influence on human life. The novelist has depicted the pitiful plight of three generations of women, as well as their struggle for existence, expression of uniqueness, and desire for self-realization.

Keywords: Social Constraints, Myth, Gender Inequality, Self-Identity, and Loneliness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Githa Hariharan is a varied Indian writer, with a body of work that includes five novels and a couple collections of short tales. She does not wish to be labelled as a "Indian lady writer," a "female novelist," or anything else.

"feminist-activist" author. Instead, she prefers to be referred to simply as a writer, and she frequently says that all titles are both restrictive and limiting. Her position on several social and political topics is unequivocal. Her works successfully depict Indian society's traditional traditions while also incorporating contemporary ideas and consciousness. She frequently asserts that she always prefers plurality and that her stories must be read as a mixture of voices. This claim unequivocally justifies her emphasis in her works on the representation of the human condition. She resorts to narrating stories in order to achieve this goal.

According to her, the true value of a novelist resides in comprehending other people's tales. The stories of other people provide the writer with both the opportunity and the scope to examine the consciousness of other people, if not in real life, then in fiction. However, as a writer, social, political, and historical knowledge, as well as a sense of responsibility, primarily nurture and strengthen access to the experiences of others.

2. THE THOUSAND FACES OF NIGHT

Githa Hariharan's first novel, *The Thousand Faces of Night*, was released in 1992 and was a significant contribution to the literary world. This work is a true watershed moment in feminist literature.

Githa Hariharan depicts the human condition sympathetically in *The Thousand Faces of Night*.

Indian women in a state of flux between tradition and modernity. She meticulously portrays their dual awareness, as a result of which we see both their submissiveness and their struggle for uniqueness through a cast of representative characters.

This novel has received greater critical attention than Githa Hariharan's previous works. Critics have investigated it from several angles, concentrating on gender inequity, superstitious beliefs, social restraints placed on women, and the search for self-identity.

Devi is about to depart America after finishing her studies when the novel begins. There, she befriends Dan, an African-American who is captivated by her beauty and spirit. Devi and Dan are given the opportunity to investigate the lives of black people. When Dan proposes to her, she declines since she cannot readily abandon her traditional identity in order to accept the western one. She returns from America to find her mother Sita alone, worried, and sensitive. Her mother's behaviour changes, and she notices it.

Her mother loves her, but she hides it behind coldness and detachment. In India, she lives in Chennai with her mother. Devi is reminded of her American friend Julie and her impulsive affection for her mother whenever she meets her mother. The relationship between the daughter and the mother progresses beyond the stages. She realises right once that the new spring of this bonding is difficult to achieve without her mother's encouragement.

Meanwhile, Sita instructs Devi in the rites and customs of planned marriages: "Like a seasoned chess player, she made her moves." I must give her credit for her sense of humour.

Devi, as the only child, allows herself to be driven by her dreams and the direction of her mother. As a result, she pursues every outlook, dresses in silk sarees, jewels, and flowers, and speaks in a humble manner in

the presence of grooms when their family visit for the marriage proposal.

Devi marries Mahesh in accordance with her mother's wishes. After her marriage, she lives a dull life with him, who is always on business trips, and she seeks solace in the companionship of her housemaid, Mayamma. Marriage, she believes, is a holy tie that links two souls. Marriage, on the other hand, appears to be an expiatory knife for her, and now, via her cuts and pricks, she gradually begins to experience and realise the pain of isolation. Devi's evaluation of the worth of marriage is tinged with unhappiness and disillusionment.

Mahesh's long absence exacerbates her loneliness and frustration. She devises techniques to distract herself from her aggravation, boredom, and loneliness. While listening to Mayamma's tragic past, she develops an affinity and connection with her, which is a unique and uncommon quality in female bonding. Mayamma's terrible story to Devi emphasises the reality of her misery and pain.

Mayamma's marital life is portrayed as a never-ending cycle of misery. She is thrown into the whirlwind of marriage at the age of twelve, when she has barely grasped the actual meaning of wifehood and womanhood. Mayamma, despite her pouting and dissatisfaction, is a strong woman who longs to forge her own identity. She never tries to flee the living horror. Devi claims that:

Mayamma had been thrown into the depths of her femininity long before she learned to swim. She'd learned about lust, the firsthand experience with the possibility for unseen bestial savagery... She snarls and pouts... She, on the other hand, was unaffected by bitterness.

Mayamma learns various survival methods and longs to assert her independence: "I have learned how to wait, when to bow my back, when to wipe the rebellious eyes dry". In fact, Mayamma's mother-in-law is so impatient that she complains when she is unable to have

a kid during her second year of marriage. Mayamma tells Devi about her agony: "When I lost my first kid, conceived after 10 years of longing and anxiety, I screamed for the first time in my life".

The kid dies during the birth, and her mother-in-law beats her, cursing her as a barren woman. She states that Mayamma's horoscope is erroneous and so demands that she perform penance in order to change its course. Mayamma looks forward to her penance like it's an old friend because it's the only option and line of action she has to survive. She ultimately decides to reclaim her life through Parvatiamma and Devi. As a result, Mayamma's existence as a wife and mother is plagued with misery and agony.

Mayamma's torturous and sad story as a wife, mother, and daughter-in-law does not end with her relationship with Parvatiamma. The novelist has purposefully allocated adequate room and has offered a complete depiction of women's quiet pains through Mayamma's memories. Even motherhood has lost its significance and worth for her with the death of her son, Raja. She is still repulsed by the presence of her womb and wishes she could tear it from within and dump it into the garbage heap to rot. In fact, she regards her womb as a tribute to her miscarried motherhood.

Mayamma's story has a catastrophic effect on Devi, who learns about the futility of being a wife and a mother via the narration. Devi finally decides to leave Mahesh and flee with Gopal for a life of freedom and joy.

Sita is very different from Mayamma in many respects. Sita, unlike Mayamma, is taught music and is not sucked into the child-marriage machine. She arrives with a dowry of 20,000 rupees, her veena, and a grim determination to be a perfect bride and mother-in-law. Sita overlooks her passion for music in order to achieve her goal, pushing other dreams to the sidelines. She appears to be ruthless in her pursuit of the ideal aim of wifedom and children.

She constructs a reticent wall that separates her from the ambiguity and links her securely to her family and home chores. Devi's disappointment with Gopal is fueled by her mother's selflessness and unwavering love over the years. Though Sita does not struggle for existence in the same way that Mayamma did, she suffers from widowhood, grief, loneliness, and emptiness.

Devi's reflection demonstrates that she is not allowed to be herself. She is deprived of the ability to make decisions in her life. She is befuddled when she eventually decides to live with Gopal. The bitter awareness of her own slip downs on her, and she says openly that she has moved far away from all her hardships. She also recognises her other failings: she was unable to be an ally to her father, and she was unable to alleviate her mother's loneliness with feminine bonding and sympathy.

She is not worried with her own identity, but rather with her shattered, unsatisfied life, which is poised to crumble and fall apart. She ultimately agrees to go to Sita and express her love to her, healing the wounds left by Sita's loneliness and Devi's betrayal. As she approaches her mother's house, she chooses to start again and recreate her connection with her mother: "She rehearsed in her mind the words, the uncompromising gaze she had to greet Sita with to show her love." To stay and fight, to make sense of it all, she'd have to start from scratch".

3. CONCLUSION

As a result of the stories of Devi, Mayamma, and Sita, *The Thousand Faces of Night* brings to life the inner-world of married Indian women's lives. Mayamma's, Sita's, and Rama's stories and Devi are expertly woven together to shed light on the inner world of Indian women's life, where hopes are dashed and survival is the only constant. Githa Hariharan has attempted to deconstruct the aura that surrounds mythological ladies and has clearly demonstrated how

reality shatters the dreamy world of mythology through her portrayal of Devi.

4. REFERENCES

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